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Addressing coastal community vulnerabilities with marine renewable energy

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Abstract

Coastal communities experience distinct socioeconomic, technical, and environmental vulnerabilities, all of which accrue heightened risk with increasingly frequent and severe climate change impacts. Marine renewable energy (MRE) offers a potential solution for mitigating some coastal community vulnerabilities, especially water-energy dependencies, while delivering promising co-benefits such as increased resilience and more sustainable energy outcomes. This paper explores coastal community vulnerabilities and service dependencies based on the local drivers that create them, with attention to climate change impacts and how they catalyze water-energy unmet needs. We utilize environmental and energy justice indicators to understand how these vulnerabilities disproportionately manifest and impact the most vulnerable community members. With those indicators, we create a weighted decision matrix tool that compares the viability of different MRE installations addressing these vulnerabilities. The indicators and tool highlight opportunities for future MRE research, pilot demonstrations, and deployments to directly respond to the vulnerabilities of coastal communities. This supports industry stakeholders in developing MRE installations that respond to community-centric values.

Keywords: coastal communities; decision matrix; marine energy

1. Introduction

Approximately 40% of the U.S. population lives in coastal counties [1]—areas existing at the nexus of land and water. The often-remote geographic nature of these coastal areas and limited availability of natural resources propagate unique socioeconomic, technical, and environmental vulnerabilities in the communities that reside there [2]. These geographic conditions often influence and drive vulnerabilities related to the prevalence of economic activities (e.g., fisheries, tourism, logging, and shipping); the social fabric of communities; access to clean and affordable energy and water provisions; and the risk of various climate change impacts. In this paper, vulnerabilities refer to “developmental, multidimensional, cross-scale” factors that affect sensitivity, exposure, and adaptive capacity—or the ability to adjust and respond—to adverse impacts [3]. These vulnerabilities have profound implications for the vitality of coastal communities, shaping the trajectory of community economics, identity, structure, and environment (both natural and built) [4]. We explore coastal community vulnerabilities across three primary dimensions—socioeconomic, technical, and environmental—and the ways in which marine renewable energy (MRE) infrastructure can serve as a supportive mechanism in addressing those vulnerabilities. We also

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explore how the identified vulnerabilities often manifest as situated dependencies, or over-reliance on particular services and practices (e.g., reliance on imported fossil fuels or a single, resource-based industry), and the stratified impacts of these dependencies along underlying socio-demographic inequalities, or indicators.

Socioeconomic, technical, and environmental vulnerabilities are not distributed equally, meaning resilience solutions must not only cater to the unique vulnerabilities of a coastal community but also seek to alleviate the disproportionate burden placed on its members. We refer to these nested demographic vulnerabilities as community indicators. For example, this includes indigenous groups who are more likely to be affected by socioeconomic, technical, and environmental vulnerabilities related to unemployment, energy quality and affordability, and proximity to natural disasters. By understanding these local realities through the lens of vulnerabilities and indicators, we can match community needs with resilience solutions, including MRE technologies.

To do so, we propose a weighted Pugh, or decision, matrix tool that integrates community vulnerabilities. The tool compares the ability of proposed MRE installations to address critical coastal community needs; it links weighted vulnerabilities to energy objectives, allowing stakeholders to compare how different MRE installations can provide benefits outside energy production. This work ultimately aims to inform community-driven planning by syncing community vulnerabilities, weighted by the percentage of the local population that is susceptible to them, to energy outcomes that improve overall quality of life and offer pathways for a more sustainable future.

2. Coastal Community Vulnerabilities

Throughout literature and documented experiences, vulnerabilities related to social and economic factors (e.g., income, employment, and housing); geographic, ecological, and climatic factors (e.g., natural disasters); and critical infrastructure factors (e.g., energy and water provisions) are repeatedly present in coastal communities and can substantially impact the livelihood, health, and wellbeing of residents [4, 5]. These pressures are often felt disproportionately between and within coastal communities, depending on underlying demographics. Here, we consider the role of intersectionality in creating stratified impacts: that various social indicators, such as race, class, and gender, create different lived experiences within coastal communities, and expose some communities and individuals to more adverse outcomes than others (Table 1).

Table 1. Examples of situated dependencies resulting from socioeconomic, technical, and environmental vulnerabilities.

	Socioeconomic	Technical	Environmental
Vulnerability	Limited availability of land and resources due to remote location	Aging electrical infrastructure and reliance on fossil fuels for primary and back-up generation	Significant likelihood of coastal erosion from climate change
Situated Dependency	Reliance on resource-extractive industries (e.g., fishing, tourism, port shipping)	High fuel costs and uncertainty in access	Reliance on (unprotected) coastal infrastructure with reliability and resilience issues

3. Socio-Demographic Indicators

Socially disadvantaged populations often face a compounded impact of socioeconomic, technical, and environmental vulnerabilities and situated dependencies due to their underlying socio-demographic inequalities. As a result, they are characterized by their lack of resources to anticipate, cope with, and recover from adverse impacts. Literature defines these socio-demographic factors based on income, educational attainment, race and ethnicity, age, and additional factors relating to cultural, political, and institutional indicators [6-10]. Socio-demographic factors or indicators can be understood as a coupling of an individual's or a community's differential propensity to risk and the conditions that make them susceptible to harm (Table 2).

Table 2 Example demographic vulnerability indicators and their resulting manifestation into individual vulnerabilities and broader unmet technical needs

Indicator	Most Vulnerable	Manifestation	Resulting Energy/critical infrastructure unmet Need(s)
Socioeconomic status	Living in poverty	Lack of transportation for evacuation, high proportional losses from disaster events (both financially and in productivity)	Lack of backup energy systems to continue normal activity during outages, inability to pay for utilities/water bills, inability to pay for household damages from natural hazards, and replacement equipment/belongings
	Renters	Damage to personal belongings, inability to reside at the residence during natural disasters	Less energy and water security due to reduced accessibility
	Individuals who are homeless or displaced	Lack of safe space/refuge during natural hazards, decreased resilience	Lack of clean water that can be used for drinking, bathing, and cooking, inability to access energy systems
Race and ethnicity	Non-white, non-Anglo	Cultural barriers, lower acceptance/trust of warnings, reside in high hazard zones	Less access to resources, language barrier, lack of resource access, lack of education, less representation in energy decision-making processes
Gender	Women	Wage gap, care-giving role, and responsibilities at home (unequal duties), domestic violence, women less likely than men to have control over environmental decisions, inequitable environmental burdens	Women left with fewer resources, less ability to afford energy for heating/cooking, security threats, diseases, disempowerment
Health	Chronically ill, seniors, children	Increased mortality, disease outbreak, post-traumatic stress	Decreased air quality, extreme weather events/temperatures leaving elders/youth more susceptible to health risks e.g., vector-borne diseases, asthma, heart disease due to climate change and exposure to pollution, greater reliance on energy for electronic medical equipment

This study synthesizes coastal community vulnerabilities, energy and critical infrastructure system dependencies, and socio-demographic and community indicators to weigh the viability of MRE installations. This approach allows us to better understand coastal community susceptibilities to disaster and measure adaptive capacity.

4. Methods

For communities to utilize MRE infrastructure to address their vulnerabilities, they must first understand how the infrastructure is capable of doing so. Standard development processes for renewable energy technologies do not guarantee that projects will create positive local impacts or avoid exacerbating vulnerabilities. Rather, it is the intention behind project development processes and siting decisions that unlocks the potential. For example, some vulnerabilities may be addressed by the location or configuration of a project, while others may be addressed through ownership models or local job creation.

Defining community priorities as they pertain to local vulnerabilities, identifying how priorities interact, and weighing tradeoffs they create can guide decision-makers to more optimal development choices. Allowing a wide range of stakeholders to engage in that assessment during early stages increases the likelihood that favorable characteristics are incorporated into the project and promotes a collective understanding of why.

To enable such an assessment, a Pugh, or decision, matrix tool was created to help community members, developers, and energy system stakeholders link community vulnerabilities to energy objectives, with the aim of fostering a collaborative decision-making environment. Pugh matrices, or decision matrices, are multi-criteria decision-making tools that compare project or product alternatives [11]. A relatively simple tool, Pugh matrices provide users with a way to compare project alternatives to a base scenario by scoring their relative ability to meet

selection criteria. The alternative with the highest score fulfills the most criteria. Creating and using a Pugh matrix can be characterized into six steps, which we define within the context of MRE infrastructure addressing community vulnerabilities (Table 3).

Table 3. Steps to constructing the Pugh matrix for MRE alternatives to address community vulnerabilities.

Step	Definition
1. Identify selection criteria	Selection criteria are defined by an MRE project's ability to engage with the socioeconomic, technical, and environmental dimensions and indicators.
2. Select reference case	Any variation of an MRE project can be used as a reference case in the Pugh matrix since the purpose of the reference case is to create a relative comparison across alternatives. A user could also input information for existing infrastructure (e.g., a coal plant) as the reference case to compare existing infrastructure to future options.
3. Compare alternatives to reference case	All alternative installation options are compared to the reference case by assessing the alternative's ability to meet the selection criteria relative to the reference case. For example, if the reference case somewhat negatively affects the fishing population (e.g., a socioeconomic vulnerability), does the alternative negatively affect the population more or less than that base case? These responses are converted to scores for a quantitative comparison.
4. Total scores	Each possible response to the selection criteria is given a score from 1–5. The higher the score, the more effective the alternative is at addressing the vulnerability. That score is multiplied by a weight, creating a weighted Pugh matrix. The weights reflect the significance of the selection criteria. In this case, the weights are dictated by the percentage of the local population affected by the vulnerability considered in the given selection criteria. The weighted scores are then totaled across the vulnerabilities for each alternative.
5. Consider hybrid scenarios	While the alternative with the highest score essentially reflects the most favorable alternative, users should consider which project characteristics created that outcome and assess whether combining alternatives or modifying some characteristics could produce a more optimal installation.
6. Make decision and record reason	After using the matrix and discussing the alternative options, users should document the final decision and why it was made, relying on the Pugh matrix as a guidepost for their reasoning.

With the goal of making the Pugh matrix easily accessible to a wide range of stakeholders, the matrix was converted into a semi-automated, user-friendly tool that is prepopulated with questions that reflect selection criteria related to projects' ability to address vulnerabilities. Although demonstrated in an exemplary manner here, the tool is meant to be participatory because outcomes are based on user judgment.

5. Results and Discussion

The Excel-based tool first asks users to fill out basic information about the reference case for the baseline and alternative projects (e.g., size, cost, technology type). These project specifications can help inform project selection, but they do not necessarily influence an installation's ability to address a given vulnerability. Thus, the tool tracks these features but does not incorporate them into the comparison. Once the project specifications are entered, the user answers a series of questions about the baseline scenario to assess its ability to address vulnerabilities as established through the selection criteria. The tool provides users with a drop-down list of potential options to standardize responses and translates them into ranked scores (Fig. 1, left). The questions primarily ask about the project's effects on the vulnerabilities and indicators discussed in Section 2 and Section 3.

The user continues to fill out the project specifications for different installation options before comparing the alternatives to the baseline for each of the selection criteria. The user is again provided with a drop-down list of options from which to select. The user then draws from disadvantaged community (DAC) data, as defined by the Justice 40 Initiative [12], to create weights for each vulnerability by selecting their location to extract data regarding local disadvantaged populations. Those weights are multiplied by the raw scores from the comparative assessment—linking together the specific populations with the vulnerabilities that affect them—and automatically populating the Pugh matrix. At this stage, the user can access the Pugh matrix to compare the results both quantitatively (Fig. 1, right) and qualitatively to consider hybrid options before documenting the final decision.

Fig. 1 Sample of the questions users fill out (left) and summary of the weighted results (right).

6. Conclusions

While this Pugh-matrix tool allows a range of stakeholders to compare alternative installation options to extract more value from MRE infrastructure with respect to addressing community vulnerabilities, several notable limitations exist. At the time of publication, the vulnerabilities considered in the tool and the weights applied to specific (more vulnerable/exposed) populations were established through existing literature. In future iterations and applications of the tool, community input on additional vulnerabilities that are significant should be included. The purpose of this work is to establish the foundation for doing so while embedding flexibility for researchers and users to continue to adapt the tool. Furthermore, the weighting process is relatively simple when, in reality, the importance that communities place on a given vulnerability may not solely be dictated by the percentage of their community that is affected by the vulnerability. Increasing the functionality of the tool to enable more complex weighting schemes that reflect nuanced community objectives is an area for future work, as is vetting the tool through comprehensive case studies conducted in cooperation with target tool users. Case studies should include the full range of stakeholders and take place early in, or prior to, the development process to engage diverse perspectives, inform decisions, and create transparency into the development process. Depending on participating communities’ interests and objectives, new versions of the tool may evaluate a single vulnerability in greater depth, introducing quantitative metrics that require more rigorous analysis and assessment than what might be possible in the existing version.

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